

MATERIAL CRUSHING BEHAVIOUR OF PULTRUDED GFRP STUB COLUMNS: EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

The lack of agreed design codes has been hindering the use of pultruded glass-fibre reinforced polymer (pGFRP) profiles. A gap in the literature is the unclear definition of “true” material crushing failure. Material properties used to estimate crushing resistance are based on coupon tests, but pGFRP profile behaviour differs at the full-section level. Understanding material crushing behaviour is crucial to develop precise and reliable design provisions. This paper presents an experimental study of material crushing in full-section pGFRP profiles of different shapes using axial compressive tests on stub columns to avoid second-order effects. Results can lead to new design guidelines for axial crushing strength and improved design curves for slender members.

KEYWORDS

GFRP profiles; material crushing; stub columns; design guidelines; experimental tests

INTRODUCTION

Recently, the use of pultruded glass-fibre reinforced polymer (pGFRP) profiles in the construction industry has become more popular as they are seen as a viable option for lightweight structures, offering high strength and durability. However, due to the relatively recent use of these profiles in structural applications, there are still gaps in the knowledge of their mechanical behaviour and geometrical characteristics.

There are several guidelines available for the design of pGFRP profiles (ACMA, 2010; CEN/TS 19101, 2022; CNR-DT 205, 2008; SBRCURnet 1850, 2017), but there is no consensus on the most appropriate design and safety checking procedures. In compression, the current approach adopted by most guidelines is known to be inaccurate (minimum between resistance to pure material failure and to pure buckling phenomenon), and there is further uncertainty when other factors come into play, such as (i) interaction between material strength and elastic buckling, (ii) coupling between different types of buckling modes, and (iii) effects of initial geometrical imperfections.

The crushing resistance of pGFRP profiles is traditionally estimated considering the material compressive resistance derived from small coupon standardized tests, carried out on laminates extracted from the cross-section's walls (ASTM D6641-14 (2014) and EN 14126 (2001)). However, recent experimental studies show that this method greatly overestimates the real crushing resistance of full-section pultruded profiles, even when they are very stocky (Lazzari et al., 2022; Ramos, 2020; Wu et al., 2022).

Turvey and Zhang (2005, 2006) reported discrepancies in the estimates of axial compression resistance obtained from coupon tests and full-section test results. The authors also reported lower shear and tensile strengths at the web-flange junction compared to the central regions of the webs and flanges. Moreover, they stated that the occurrence of defects has a higher probability in full-section specimens, when compared to small-scale coupons. Similarly, Ramos (2020) identified four potential factors contributing to the lower resistance to material crushing observed in full-section compression tests compared to coupon tests: (i) mechanical property heterogeneity across the cross-section

(namely in web-flange junctions), (ii) variations in the compressive strength obtained from different test standards, (iii) increased likelihood of defects in full-section tests (“size effects”), and (iv) influence of surface end defects (lack of flatness) in full-section compression specimens. Recently, Wu *et al.* (2022) conducted tests on pGFRP channel columns with lengths ranging from 100 mm to 1400 mm. The authors observed significantly lower compressive strength estimates from coupon tests for stub columns measuring 100 mm and 200 mm in length. They attributed this to (i) irregularities in the cross-section shape, leading to non-uniform stress distribution, (ii) non-uniform fiber distribution caused by the pultrusion process and material imperfections, and (iii) local crushing resulting from stress concentrations or material imperfection, which interact with the local buckling phenomenon of the flange or web.

To illustrate the impact of coupon tests and stub column tests on determining the actual material compressive strength of pGFRP profiles, Figure 1 presents the reduction strength factor (χ) plotted against the column slenderness (λ) based on experimental tests conducted by Wu *et al.* (2022). The experimental ultimate axial stress (f_u) is normalized by the material compressive strength obtained from small coupon laminates, extracted from the web of the cross-section ($f_{x,c}$), or from the average ultimate stress from stub column tests (f_{sc}). The plot is based on the slenderness ratio (λ), which is defined as the square root of the ratio between the material crushing strength and the critical buckling stress. The global buckling slenderness is determined by the global buckling stress (f_{crG}), while the local buckling slenderness is determined by the local buckling stress (f_{crL}). The perfect column curve is also illustrated in Figure 1 and defined as $\chi = 1$ for $\lambda \leq 1$ and $\chi = 1/\lambda^2$ for $\lambda > 1$. The graphs in Figure 1 illustrates the effect of the estimates of the crushing strength given from coupon tests and stub columns tests, in a classical χ vs λ plot, indicating that the stub column tests shift the data towards the perfect column curve, with some notable strength reduction to possible crushing-buckling interaction.

Figure 1: Reduction strength factor (χ) versus slenderness ratio (λ) for a pGFRP C-section column tested by Wu *et al.* (2022): (a) global buckling failure and (b) local buckling failure, normalized by material crushing strength given from coupon tests ($f^* = f_{x,c}$) or stub column tests ($f^* = f_{sc}$).

The objective of this study is to investigate the material crushing failure of pGFRP profiles by comparing their actual full-section resistance with predictions based on material compressive strength obtained from standardized small-scale coupon tests. The study presented in the paper was developed in two stages: (i) an analysis of the mechanical behaviour of five stub columns, including the evaluation of stress-strain curves using strain gauges and video-extensometer data, and (ii) a parametric experimental study involving 45 stub columns to assess their compressive resistance across a range of slenderness values within the stocky column range ($0.4 < \lambda < 0.7$).

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

The experimental study included the mechanical characterization of the material through standardized coupon tests, as well as the testing of full-section stub columns. The experimental campaign was

conducted at the Laboratory of Structures and Strength of Materials (LERM) of the Department of Civil Engineering of Instituto Superior Técnico, University of Lisbon.

Materials

The pGFRP profiles considered in the present study comprised four different cross-sections and were produced by two manufacturers (Creative Composites Group, 2022; Strongwell, 2020). The main characteristics of the profiles are summarized in Table 1, including the cross-section shape, the manufacturer, the resin type, the nominal dimensions (height \times width \times thickness, see Figure 2) and the label name used in the present study.

Table 1: Characteristics of the pultruded GFRP profiles.

Cross-section	Manufacturer	Resin	Nominal Dimensions (mm)	Label
I-section	Creative Pultrusions	Polyester	152.4 \times 76.2 \times 6.35	CI6
C-section	Strongwell	Vinyl Ester	76.2 \times 22.23 \times 6.35	C76-6
I-section	Strongwell	Vinyl Ester	101.6 \times 50.8 \times 6.35	I102-6
Square Hollow Section (SHS)	Strongwell	Vinyl Ester	101.6 \times 101.6 \times 6.35	S102-6

Figure 2: Pultruded GFRP profiles geometry and reference name (dimensions in mm).

Coupon tests

The mechanical properties of the profiles were obtained from standardized tests on small-scale coupons extracted from the walls of the profiles. The mechanical properties of the profile CI6 were retrieved from Almeida-Fernandes *et al.* (2020) (except the Poisson ratio $\nu_{xy,c}$, which was reported by Ramos (2020)). For the remaining profiles, the properties were determined in the scope of the present experimental campaign. It should be mentioned that the compressive strength in the longitudinal direction was determined using the combined loading compression method (CLC, ASTM D6641-14 (2014) and EN 14126 (2001)). For the C76-6 and I102-6 profiles, the coupon specimens were extracted from the web of the profiles only (due to the size limitations of the walls of the flanges), as indicated in Figure 2.

The tests were conducted in a universal testing machine (UTM), from Intron, model 5989, with a capacity of 600 kN. A video-extensometer system was employed to determine the relative displacements of various target points marked on the specimens, enabling the assessment of deformations. This system comprises a 10-bit Sony CCD XCLU100 camera connected to a Fujinon F35SA-1 lens with a range of 35 mm and aperture ranging from 1.4 to 22, with an accuracy of ± 0.005 mm. The device is placed on a tripod for added stability. One of the key advantages of this approach is the ability to capture strains in various directions within the plane of the specimens, avoiding the need for disposable strain gauges. Figure 3 provides, as an example, the stress-strain and transverse vs. longitudinal strains (illustrating the Poisson effect) plots, obtained from the CLC test of a I102-6 profile specimen; the curves illustrate the predominantly linear behaviour and brittle failure. More information about the compressive properties measured in the longitudinal direction for the I102-6 profile is given in Table 2, namely the compressive strength in the longitudinal direction ($f_{x,c}$) and the elastic properties (modulus of elasticity in longitudinal $E_{x,c}$ and transversal $E_{y,c}$ directions, major Poisson ratio $\nu_{xy,c}$ and shear modulus G_{xy}).

Figure 3: Longitudinal compressive behaviour of six I102-6 specimens coupon test under CLC method: (a) longitudinal compressive stress vs. longitudinal compressive strain, and (b) transverse vs. longitudinal strains.

Table 2: Mechanical properties from coupon tests of the pGFRP profiles (x is the longitudinal (pultrusion) direction, y is the in-plane perpendicular direction, and subscript *c* refers to a property measured in compression)

Reference Name	Property	Strength		Elastic properties			
		$f_{x,c}^2$	$E_{y,c}^2$	$E_{x,c}^3$	ν_{yx}^4	$\nu_{xy,c}^5$	G_{xy}^6
		MPa	GPa	GPa	-	-	GPa
CI6 ¹	Mean	437	10.90	24.60	0.15	0.34	4.20
	COV	6%	12%	3%		17%	14%
	<i>n</i>	6	6	6		15	6
C76-6	Mean	561	12.01	23.19	0.17	0.33	3.40
	COV	4%	6%	5%		5%	5%
	<i>n</i>	5	6	6		6	6
I102-6	Mean	515	10.57	26.51	0.13	0.33	3.51
	COV	6%	9%	3%		3%	9%
	<i>n</i>	5	6	6		6	6
S102-6	Mean	680	9.66	28.46	0.12	0.34	4.59
	COV	8%	11%	8%		7%	14%
	<i>n</i>	7	6	8		8	8

¹ CI6 mechanical properties given by (Almeida-Fernandes et al., 2020; Ramos, 2020).

² CI6 according to ASTM D6641-14 (2014), and C76-6, I102-6, and S102-6 according to EN 14126 (2001).

³ CI6 according to ASTM D6641-14 (2014), and C76-6, I102-6, and S102-6 according to ASTM D695-02a (2002).

⁴ Given from the relationship $\nu_{yx} = E_y \nu_{xy} / E_x$

⁵ CI6 (Ramos, 2020) according to ASTM D6641-14 (2014), and C76-6, I102-6, and S102-6 according to ASTM D695-02a (2002).

⁶ According to ASTM D5379-12 (2012).

Stub column tests

Figure 4 depicts the apparatus and experimental configuration employed for the stub column tests. The tests were conducted in the same UTM used for the coupon tests and were monitored (in CI6 series only) with the same video-extensometer system. Steel round flat base plates with a thickness of 25 mm were clamped to both crossheads to ensure pure compression testing. The tests were performed under displacement control, at a rate of 1.00 mm/min. It is important to mention that the stub column tests were performed according to recommendations of previous studies (Cardoso, 2014; Ramos, 2020); and also according to the recent standard procedure for full-section compression tests on pultruded profiles (ISO 23930 (2023)), which specifies the same procedure described in Annex B of GB/T 31539 (2015).

Figure 4: Setup for stub column compression tests.

To guarantee that the columns were in fact stub, their length was determined so that the critical buckling load was significantly higher than the material's crushing load. Cardoso *et al.* (2014) suggested that material crushing failure in columns and plates can be predicted when both the relative plate slenderness (λ_L) and relative column slenderness (λ_G) are below 0.7. Slenderness was calculated as the square root of the ratio between the material's compressive strength and the critical buckling stress. The critical buckling stresses, corresponding to local and global buckling modes, were obtained from elastic buckling analysis using *FStr* software (Lazzari & Batista, 2021). As mentioned earlier, the material's compressive strength was first determined from coupon tests. With the compressive strength and the slenderness limit known (*e.g.*, $\lambda_{lim} = 0.7$, according to Cardoso *et al.* (2014)), the limit critical stress associated with a specific longitudinal length (L) could then be calculated. By considering the material properties presented in Table 2, a target limit length could be defined for the stub specimens corresponding to the different cross-sections.

In order to minimize stress concentrations (due to lack of flatness of end edges) and avoid premature failure of the flanges (unlike what was reported in previous tests (Ramos, 2020)), the specimens in this study were carefully prepared with flat end surfaces. The flatness and parallelism of the surface ends has been checked with a high precision geometric measurement. Forty points have been measured, 21 points per surface, with assistance of a 3D coordinate measuring machine (CMM). More information about the setup and the methodology of the measurements are given in the study of Lazzari *et al.* (2023). Based on the measurements, it was possible to extract the error in parallelism, evaluated as the difference of the maximum and minimum distances between a linear fitted plane in one end surface, compared to the points in the other plane, as illustrated in Figure 5. These measurements were conducted on the CI6-6 specimen, and the error in parallelism was found to be 0.093 mm, much lower than the limit deviation defined in ISO 23930 (2023), of 0.5 mm. In addition, the parallelism in degrees was evaluated as 0.038° and the flatness of each end surface was 0.035 mm and 0.058 mm.

Figure 5: Stub column tests, series CI6: (a) geometry measurement surface points (CI6-6), and (b) overview of test specimens.

A total of 50 stub column specimens were tested. In the first stage, 5 specimens of profile CI6 were tested, with limit length of 64 mm ($\lambda_{lim} = 0.7$); they were used to evaluate the stress-strain behaviour, with data gathered from strain-gauges and the video-extensometer device. The second stage involved 45 specimens (C76-6, I102-6 and S102-6), which were used for a parametric study with the objective of evaluating the ultimate capacity of stub columns under a range of slenderness values ($0.4 < \lambda_{lim} < 0.7$). For this experimental parametric study, using the C76-6, I102-6 and S102-6 profiles, each cross-section was tested under 5 different lengths: (i) four lengths were chosen based in a set of 4 slenderness values (*i.e.*, $\lambda_{lim} = [0.4; 0.5; 0.6; 0.7]$), (ii) one length was chosen according to the limitations included in the standard ISO 23930 (2023), (iii) 3 repetitions for each length were made, and (iv) no strain data was recorded, only the ultimate compressive strength (more information about the length of the specimens is provided in the results and discussion section, in Table 3).

During the tests, data was collected from three sources: (i) the test machine, which recorded load vs. crosshead displacement curves, (ii) the video extensometer, which recorded relative displacements of targets on the profile's web and flanges (only for series CI6), and (iii) strain gauges (only for specimens CI6-4 and CI6-5).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Stress-strain behaviour of CI6 stub column

Figure 6 illustrates the axial stress-strain behaviour under axial loading, with strains being measured using both a video extensometer (VE) and strain gauges (SG). Three strain gauges were strategically positioned at the midpoint of the web and flanges, following the guidelines outlined in the ISO 23930 (2023) standard. The reference points for the video extensometer were located 16 mm from each surface end. While there may be slight variations in the alignment between the strain gauges and video extensometer reference points (*e.g.*, VE1 and SG3), the results demonstrate a similar stiffness behaviour. This similarity is evident from the consistent slope observed in the elastic region of the stress-strain curve derived from the strain measurements obtained from the flanges of the profile.

One notable observation from Figure 6 is the presence of a toe region at the flanges at the initial stage of the test, for average compressive stresses (in the cross-section) spanning from 0 MPa to 20 MPa. This phenomenon can be attributed to a similar physical effect described in the ASTM D695-15 (2015) standard and previously discussed by Lazzari *et al.* (2022). The possible causes for this behavior include the irregular flatness of the specimen's end surfaces, as highlighted by Ramos (2020), or the potential misalignment of the profile within the testing machine. Despite the efforts to ensure specimen centering and end edges flatness, small imperfections and material heterogeneity inevitably influence the stress distribution and subsequently affect strains. However, it is important to note that the toe region effect is primarily observed at the initial stage of the test. Subsequently, a distinct region of linear behavior, ranging from 80 MPa to 160 MPa, becomes prominent, with the

web being the last wall element that initiates deformation after an average compressive stress of 80 MPa is reached. This linear region is considered significant for determining the elastic modulus in compression for the full-section profile.

Figure 6: Axial stress-strain behaviour of the CI6-5 stub column, with strains measured with the video-extensometer (VE) and strain-gauges (SG).

Regarding the stiffness measurements of the stub columns, Figure 7 presents the apparent values of the “local” longitudinal elastic modulus (in compression) obtained for each specified target line using the VE. For all tested specimens, a mean value of the full-section longitudinal elastic modulus (in compression) of 29.8 GPa (COV of 13%) was obtained from the “local” estimates, weighted based on their respective areas of influence. The “local” estimates of the elastic modulus revealed notable consistency for the target alignments in the flanges, with coefficients of variation (COV) around ~10%. In contrast, the target alignments in the web exhibited significantly higher COV values (13% to 29%), especially in the central alignment (zone 3), reflecting a higher “local” stiffness, compared to the zones close to the flanges (zone 2 and 4).

Figure 7: Longitudinal elastic moduli in compression, obtained in the stub column tests for series CI6.

The comparison between the elastic moduli presented in Figure 7 with those obtained from coupon tests in previous studies (Almeida-Fernandes et al., 2020; Ramos, 2020), listed in Table 2 and indicated in Figure 7, shows that the coupon tests provide lower average values than the full-section tests (12% to 33% lower); conversely, as reported in

Table 3, the compressive strength values obtained from the stub-column tests are 57% lower than those provided by coupon tests.

Parametric study on stub columns

The present parametric study investigates several stocky columns with local slenderness ratios ranging from 0.4 to 0.7. The objective is to examine the influence of column slenderness on the ultimate capacity of stub columns and determine the threshold slenderness for which material crushing failure occurs without influence of buckling phenomena.

Table 3 presents the strength results of the stub column tests carried out within this study. For each type of cross section and specimen length, it includes the ultimate capacity of the stub column (f_{sc}) and compares it to the compressive strength obtained from coupon tests ($f_{x,c}$). The ratio of stub column axial capacity to coupon compressive strength ($f_{sc}/f_{x,c}$) ranged from 0.43 to 0.69. Furthermore, specimens C76-6, I102-6, and S102-6, which share the same manufacturer and material description (see Table 1), exhibit an average compressive strength (from coupon tests) of 597 MPa with COV of 14%, while stub column tests yield an average strength of 341 MPa with COV of 5%. This finding is in line with previous studies (Correia, 2004; Lazzari et al., 2022; Ramos, 2020; Wu et al., 2022).

Table 3: Strength results of the stub column tests (f_{sc}) and comparison with CLC coupon tests ($f_{x,c}$).

Specimen	L (mm)	Stub Columns				Coupons				$f_{sc} / f_{x,c}$
		n	f_{sc} (MPa)		$\lambda_{L,sc}$	n	$f_{x,c}$ (MPa)		$\lambda_{L,c}$	
			Mean	COV			Mean	COV		
CI6	64	5	190	8%	0.46	6	437	6%	0.70	0.43
C76-6-17*	17*	3	366	2%	0.33	5	561	4%	0.41	0.65
C76-6-30	30	3	363	0%	0.33	5	561	4%	0.41	0.65
C76-6-40	40	3	342	3%	0.39	5	561	4%	0.51	0.61
C76-6-49	49	3	347	2%	0.47	5	561	4%	0.60	0.62
C76-6-59	59	3	359	2%	0.56	5	561	4%	0.70	0.64
I102-6-31*	31*	3	325	1%	0.30	5	515	6%	0.38	0.63
I102-6-33	33	3	326	5%	0.32	5	515	6%	0.40	0.63
I102-6-41	41	3	328	6%	0.39	5	515	6%	0.50	0.64
I102-6-50	50	3	349	4%	0.49	5	515	6%	0.60	0.68
I102-6-60	60	3	358	2%	0.58	5	515	6%	0.70	0.69
S102-6-117*	117*	3	304	1%	0.86	7	680	8%	1.28	0.45
S102-6-32	32	3	325	4%	0.30	7	680	8%	0.43	0.48
S102-6-37	37	3	331	5%	0.35	7	680	8%	0.50	0.49
S102-6-45	45	3	315	3%	0.41	7	680	8%	0.60	0.46
S102-6-54	54	3	355	3%	0.51	7	680	8%	0.70	0.52

* Longitudinal length according to ISO 23930, $L = 3r$ (where r is the minor radius of gyration) and $L < 5t$ (for walls with free edges, when it is possible, due to limitation of the profile dimension).

Figure 8 displays, as an example, the axial force vs. crosshead displacement curves for the C76-6 specimens. The curves demonstrate nearly linear elastic behaviour until the occurrence of abrupt and brittle failure. This characteristic behaviour was observed consistently across all 45 tested specimens, indicating the occurrence of pure material crushing failure.

Figure 8: Axial force vs. crosshead displacement behaviour of the stub columns C76-6.

Figure 9-(a) illustrates the relationship between the reduction strength factor (χ) and the slenderness ratio (λ) for the tested specimens, using the concept introduced in Figure 1. The reduction strength factor is determined by normalizing the stub column strength (f_{SC}) with the coupon compressive strength ($f_{x,c}$) provided in Table 2. The critical buckling stress (f_{crL}) is obtained from the *FStr* software (Lazzari & Batista, 2021), considering local buckling as the critical mode. As depicted in Figure 9-(a), the reduction strength factor exhibits a consistent plateau for each cross-section, which is a possible indication that the stub column has reached its material's ultimate strength (when $\lambda < 0.7$). However, it is important to note that when comparing results across different cross-sections, the reduction strength factor exhibits distinct plateaus. This behaviour may be attributed to the influence of cross-section geometry on material crushing behaviour, including weaker wall junctions and material heterogeneity resulting from the pultrusion process, as well as potential small irregular flatness of the specimens or misalignment of the profile within the testing machine, even though great care was taken in the end surfaces preparation and specimen alignment in the test machine.

Figure 9: Pultruded GFRP stub column tests, including those prepared according to the ISO 23930 (2023) standard: (a) reduction strength factor (χ) vs. slenderness ratio (λ) and (b) slenderness associated with the coupon test strength $\lambda_{L,c}$ compared to the slenderness associated with the stub column tests average strength $\lambda_{L,SC}$.

Another relevant aspect for discussion is the standard procedure defined in ISO 23930 (2023) for determining the full-section compressive strength, which prompts a few remarks. Firstly, the standard requires a test speed equivalent to 10% of the specimen's longitudinal length by minute. However, this test speed may be excessively high for capturing the material crushing behaviour in a quasi-static stub column test (e.g., 11.7 mm/min for the S102-6-117 specimens, leading to a total test time below 1 min for specimens C76-6-17 and I102-6-31). Secondly, the standard imposes restrictions on slenderness and width-to-thickness ratio to prevent second order effects, which is based on geometric slenderness, instead of a normalized slenderness. To prevent global buckling, the geometric slenderness ratio is defined (in ISO 23930) as the length divided by the minor radius of gyration, and it must be less than 3. Similarly, to avoid local buckling, the width-to-thickness ratio (where width is the larger dimension between the length of the stub column and the wall's cross-section width) should be below specific thresholds: (i) 5 for simply supported plates, (ii) 8 for doubly edge supported plates, and (iii) 5 for non-double symmetrical sections. It is important to note that these limitations do not take into account the prediction of material strength, thus potentially resulting in inaccurate estimates of the maximum length required to prevent buckling phenomena. Figure 9-(a) clearly demonstrates that specimens complying with the provisions given in ISO 23930 (2023) may exhibit inadequate slenderness values, not representing the actual slenderness of the structural member. In particular, the S102-6-117 specimen closely aligned with the pure buckling curve, implying a potential interaction between

crushing and buckling. The slenderness limitations outlined in the aforementioned standard could be more accurately estimated if material strength was taken into consideration.

In this context, a more appropriate estimate of slenderness can be obtained by accounting for the material strength (obtained using the CLC standardized procedures for coupon testing). Figure 9-(b) shows the local slenderness obtained using two different material failure strengths, obtained from (i) coupon tests ($\lambda_{L,c}$) and (ii) stub column tests ($\lambda_{L,SC}$). Although the estimates of material failure using stub column tests yield lower values compared to those obtained from coupon tests (less than 10%), they provide a conservative and reasonable approach, unlike the slenderness concept used in ISO 23930 (2023). This trend can also be observed in the data of Figure 1.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The study presented in this paper aimed to investigate the material crushing behaviour of pultruded GFRP stub columns by comparing the resistances predicted from standardized small-scale coupon tests and full-section experiments. The results show that the former estimates are significantly higher than the compressive strength obtained from short column full-section tests, confirming previous findings.

In terms of stress-strain behaviour, the full-section tests revealed a clear linear behaviour with a distinct toe effect during the initial stage. This effect may be attributed to factors such as profile-machine alignment, material heterogeneity, or surface flatness irregularities despite careful preparation of test specimens and test setup. Additionally, there was a noticeable variation in axial strains across the cross-section width, with a clear trend of decreasing “local” elastic modulus estimates from the middle of the web to the flanges.

Regarding the parametric study on stub columns, several noteworthy observations can be made regarding the accurate determination of the full-section compressive strength. Firstly, some of the recommendations outlined in the ISO 23930 (2023) standard appear inadequate for assessing the compressive strength of stub columns. Alternatively, a more appropriate approach for estimating the “true” slenderness and capturing the pure material crushing behaviour of the full section involves adopting a similar procedure to that proposed by Cardoso *et al.* (2014). This revised slenderness criterion limits both plate and member slenderness to a maximum value of 0.7. This refined slenderness approach takes into consideration the occurrence of pure material crushing failure (strength estimates obtained from coupon tests) while accounting for the phenomenon of pure elastic buckling.

Future work will focus on the use of Digital Image Correlation (DIC) to understand in further depth the strain distributions along the cross-section of pGFRP columns. Experimental campaigns will include additional cross-sectional shapes and longer, slender columns to explore the combined effects of buckling behaviour and material crushing. Moreover, future numerical analyses will consider the progressive failure of the material (Gonilha *et al.*, 2021), influence of walls junction, frictional contact between end plates and pGFRP profiles and initial geometrical imperfections measured from real scale profiles. Lastly, a reliability study is planned to calibrate correction factors (to take into account differences in compressive strength from small-scale coupon tests and full-section stub column tests) as well as partial factors for design purposes.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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